

Analysing The Needs of English Language For Graduate and Non-Graduating Accounting Students

at The Faculty of Economics and Commerce

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to determine the specific English language needs of accounting students at Alasmarya Islamic University (AIU), in the Faculty of Economics and Commerce (FEC). Employing Hutchinson and Waters' (1987) approach to needs analysis, this study explored the perceptions of accounting students and their lecturers at FEC regarding the essential English language skills and sub-skills for accounting students. Additionally, it delved into the students' self-assessment of their English language proficiency and their desired areas of language training. Quantitative data were gathered using an adapted questionnaire distributed to students and lecturers. The study revealed that all proposed language skills are deemed necessary for accounting students at FEC, from the perspective of both sample members. Furthermore, the study identified varying perceptions regarding the importance of specific language sub-skills. The results have shown that the students have evaluated themselves to be of a low level of proficiency in speaking and writing and of an average level in listening and reading language skills. However, the results showed that participants strongly expressed a need for comprehensive English language training, emphasizing the importance of developing all sub-skills.

Keywords: English Language Needs, Needs Analysis, English Skills and English Sub-Skills.

المستخلص

هدفت هذه الدراسة إلى التعرف على احتياجات اللغة الإنجليزية لطلاب المحاسبة في كلية الاقتصاد والتجارة بالجامعة الأسمرية الإسلامية. وباستخدام منهجية Hutchinson and Waters (1987) لتحليل الاحتياجات، بحثت هذه الدراسة في تصورات طلاب المحاسبة والأساتذة تجاه مهارات اللغة الإنجليزية الرئيسية والمهارات الفرعية اللازمة لدراسة المحاسبة

في كلية الاقتصاد والتجارة، وتصورات الطلاب تجاه مستوى كفاءتهم في اللغة الإنجليزية، والمهارات الفرعية اللغوية التي يأملون في الحصول على تدريب فيها. لجمع البيانات، تم استخدام طريقة كمية تتمثل في استخدام الاستبيان والذي تم تعديله ليتناسب مع متطلبات الدراسة وقد استعمل لجمع آراء الطلاب والأساتذة. وقد أظهرت نتائج الدراسة أن جميع المهارات اللغوية الرئيسية المقترحة ضرورية لطلاب المحاسبة في كلية الاقتصاد والتجارة من منظور كلا افراد العينتين. كما كشفت الدراسة عن التصورات المختلفة تجاه المهارات الفرعية اللغوية المهمة. وقد أظهرت النتائج أن الطلاب قد قيموا أنفسهم على أنهم في مستوى منخفض من الكفاءة في مهارتي التحدث والكتابة ومستوى متوسط في مهارتي الاستماع والقراءة اللغوية. ومع ذلك، أظهرت النتائج أن المشاركين أعربوا بقوة عن الحاجة إلى تدريب شامل على اللغة الإنجليزية، مؤكداً على أهمية تطوير جميع المهارات الفرعية. الكلمات المفتاحية: احتياجات اللغة الإنجليزية، تحليل الاحتياجات، مهارات اللغة الإنجليزية، والمهارات الفرعية للغة الإنجليزية.

1. BACKGROUND AND PROBLEM

1.1 Introduction

For centuries, education has been a top priority for communities and countries everywhere. They see it as a foundation for progress, driving the development of their societies. This is evident in the on-going efforts to update and improve curriculums to address the ever-changing needs of the world. A prime example is the focus on English, which has become the global language of communication. The English language plays a vital role in modern education, academic advancement, and professional opportunities.

In Libya, English is the first foreign language taught to students from their early elementary stages to their high tertiary levels. Despite the prominence of English in Libya, Mohsen (2014) found that Libyan students across various educational levels, including college, exhibit low English proficiency. Based on that, it can be hypothesized that Libyan students fail their English courses. However, on the contrary, students succeed, as indicated by Ramadan (2020) in his article where he pointed out the reasons why students succeed despite their poor English proficiency. Ramadan included these reasons: "rote-learning (memorization), the testing system (content replication vs. content relevance) and the mal-practice (cheating in exams)" (p.259) .

At the tertiary level in Libya, the recognition of English as a crucial international lingua franca is evident. All universities mandate English language courses for students, regardless of their major. Moreover, specialized English courses are offered to cater to the specific needs of students pursuing various fields of study. Alasmarya Islamic University

(AIU) is not an exception where the Faculty of Economics and Commerce (FEC) has adopted the series of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) books called: Career Paths: Business English . According to its website "asmarya.edu.ly/economy/" The Faculty of Economics and Commerce (FEC): was established as one of the faculties of Nasser University in Zliten in 1991. Its affiliation was restored to Al-Mergib University in 2001, and it continued under Al-Mergib University until its affiliation was transferred to Alasmarya Islamic University in 2013. The faculty offers six programs: Accounting, Economics, Political Science, Banking and Finance, Business Administration, and Marketing (Anonymous, 2024). The Accounting Department was established alongside the inception of FEC in 1991 as mentioned in its website "asmarya.edu.ly/economy/". The Career Paths: Business English book, authored by John Taylor and Jeff Zeter and published by Express Publishing UK, is used in the curriculum of FEC. The English language is taught to students as a general subject before the student specializes in a specific major at the faculty .

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite English's global dominance in business and finance, Libyan accounting students often face challenges in mastering the language. This deficiency hinders their ability to understand international accounting standards, access global literature, and effectively communicate within the professional sphere (Ben-Madani, 2016). The need for English for Specific Purposes (ESP) in accounting has become increasingly apparent. However, Libyan educational institutions often overlook this requirement when designing academic programs. This oversight is particularly problematic given the growing internationalization of the accounting profession and the potential for Libyan accountants to work in multinational settings or pursue advanced degrees.

1.3 Research Questions

This study is conducted to answer these questions:

What are the English language needs of accounting students at FEC on the basis of their perceptions?

How important are the English language skills and sub-skills for graduate and non-graduating accounting students at FEC?

What are the English language lacks of graduate and non-graduating accounting students at FEC?

What are the English language wants of graduate and non-graduating accounting students at FEC?

What are the English language needs of graduate and non-graduating accounting students at FEC on the basis of their lecturers' perceptions?

How important are the English language skills and sub-skills for graduate and non-graduating accounting students at FEC?

1.4 Purposes of the Study

The purposes of this study are to:

Identify the English language needs of graduate and non-graduating accounting students at accounting department according to their own perceptions .

Identify the English language needs of graduate and non-graduating accounting students according to their lecturers' perceptions.

Provide teachers, course designers, and those who are in charge of education at FEC with guidelines that help furnish new ESP courses for graduate and non-graduating accounting students that meet all their needs.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study's significance lies in:

This study identifies the specific English language needs of undergraduate and graduate accounting students at FEC. By understanding their proficiency and gaps in English language skills, the study aims to provide valuable insights for developing more effective and targeted English language courses within the accounting curriculum. These tailored courses can better equip students with the language skills necessary to succeed in the accounting profession.

It offers a significant contribution to understanding the English language needs of both undergraduate and graduate accounting students at FEC. The findings can inform decisions made by faculty and administrators regarding the development of more effective English language instruction within the Accounting Department.

Underscoring the critical role of needs analysis in effective course development. By identifying the specific English language needs of accounting students at FEC, this research provides a valuable foundation for designing targeted and relevant courses that meet their learning requirements.

Encouraging Libyan researchers to delve into similar research areas and pave the way for future studies.

Contributing to the literature of needs analysis in Libya and the Libyan context in this field.

1.6 METHODOLOGY

This study aimed to investigate the specific English language needs of accounting students at the Faculty of Economics and Commerce (FEC). To achieve this goal, a quantitative research design was employed. Two sets of questionnaires were used, one for the students and another for the lecturers and copies of them were distributed to both samples. The questionnaires were adapted from Al-Tamimi and Shuib (2010) to suit the situation .

The participants of this study were the students and lecturers in the Accounting Department at FEC. For the students' sample: the population of this study was all the graduate and non-graduating accounting students. A random sample of male and female students was chosen to represent the entire student population. For the lecturers' sample: the population of this research was all the accounting lecturers at FEC from which a sample were drawn.

A total of 45 questionnaires were distributed to accounting students, of which 40 (88.9%) were valid for analysis. Additionally, 15 questionnaires were distributed to accounting lecturers, with 13 (86.7%) being valid for analysis. For the purpose of data reliability, the Alpha test, a measure of internal consistency devised by Lee Cronbach in 1951, was implemented

2 .LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 English for Specific Purposes (ESP)

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is a branch of English language teaching that focuses on the specific needs of learners in various professional and academic contexts. As Jordan (1997) noted, ESP can be broadly categorized into two main strands: Firstly, English for Occupational/Vocational/Professional Purposes (EOP/EVP/EPP). This category addresses the language requirements of learners in specific jobs or professions. It encompasses areas such as medicine, engineering, aviation, hospitality, and more. Secondly, English for Academic Purposes (EAP) which focuses on the language skills needed for academic success, including listening, note-taking, reading, writing, and participating in discussions. It caters to learners at various educational levels, from undergraduate to postgraduate studies. Within EAP, we can further distinguish between, English for Specific Academic Purposes (ESAP) and English for General Academic

Purposes (EGAP). In essence, ESP provides tailored language instruction to meet the unique needs of learners in various professional and academic domains, ensuring that they can effectively communicate and succeed in their chosen fields.

English language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) are integral to both English for Academic Purposes (EAP) and English for Occupational/Vocational/Professional Purposes (EOP/EVP/EPP). While Dudley-Evans and John (1998) argue that these skills don't differ significantly between EAP and EOP, they acknowledge the importance of each in both contexts. The significance of each of these skills in ESP can be explored as follows :

2.1.1 Reading is often considered the cornerstone of ESP, as it's essential for understanding the specialized language of a particular field (McDonough, 1984; Hirvela, 2013) .

2.1.2 Writing is another critical skill, especially in academic and professional settings (Hyland, 2013). Effective writing requires understanding and adapting to different writing conventions and genres within specific fields.

2.1.3 Speaking is essential but often challenging for second language learners (Dudley-Evans & John, 1998). In the early stages of ESP, speaking skills might have been overlooked, but their importance is now widely recognized.

2.1.4 Listening has been primarily studied in academic contexts within ESP (Goh, 2013). However, listening is a demanding skill in all areas of ESP due to the specialized nature of the language and the need to understand complex information.

2.2 Syllabus and Course Design

A syllabus defines the learning objectives of a course. Its design involves selecting and sequencing content, considering learner needs, and setting clear objectives (Hutchison & Waters, 1987; Harmer, 2001; Jordan, 1997). Jordan (1997) identified three primary types of syllabi: content-focused, skills-based, or process-oriented approaches. Content-focused syllabi prioritize specific language features, while skills-based syllabi emphasize language use and proficiency. Process-oriented syllabi focus on the learning process itself, involving learners actively in their education .

Course design approaches vary as well, Hutchinson and Waters (1987) proposed three approaches: Language-centered approaches prioritize

the target language but may neglect learner needs. Skills-centered approaches emphasize language skills and strategies but may overlook specific language requirements. A learning-centered approach acknowledges the complexity of learning, involving learners, teachers, and the community.

Effective ESP course design involves several stages. Dudley-Evans and John (1998) outlined the following stages of course design: Needs analysis helps identify learner requirements. Course design determines the syllabus, instructions, and other course aspects. Materials selection ensures appropriate resources. Teaching and learning practices should align with needs analysis. Finally, evaluation measures course effectiveness and goal achievement.

An effective ESP course design requires a comprehensive approach that considers syllabus types, course design approaches, and the stages of course development. By aligning these elements with learner needs and utilizing appropriate teaching and evaluation strategies, educators can create engaging and impactful ESP courses.

2.3 Needs Analysis

Needs analysis is a crucial component of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) that involves identifying and determining the specific language requirements of learners. Richards (2001) defines it as "procedures used to collect information about learners' needs" (p.51). Dudley-Evans and John (1998) emphasize its importance as a key stage in ESP, enabling researchers to determine the "what and how" of a course, leading to a highly focused curriculum. Hutchinson and Waters (1987) highlight that this "awareness of the need" distinguishes ESP courses from general English courses. By understanding learners' specific language requirements, ESP educators can tailor their instruction to meet their unique needs and maximize learning opportunities.

2.3.1 Steps to needs analysis

There are some steps to needs analysis that can be followed. Jordan (1997) has mentioned the following steps in need analysis :

Purpose of analysis

Delimit student population

Decide upon the approach/approaches

Acknowledge constraints/limitations

Select methods of collecting data

Collect data

Analyse and interpret results

Determine objectives

Implement decisions

Evaluate procedures and results

2.3.2 Approaches to needs analysis

Various approaches to needs analysis have been proposed in the literature. These approaches can be categorized as follows:

Systematic approach: This approach involves eliciting learners' needs from both learners themselves and educational institutions. However, it has been criticized for ignoring actual-world needs and overemphasizing perceived needs (Jordan, 1997).

Sociolinguistic approach: This approach focuses on learners' communication needs, including goals, medium, tactics, and strategies. It emphasizes target situation analysis (Hutchinson & Waters, 1987; Jordan, 1997).

Learner-centered approach: This approach distinguishes between subjective (cognitive and affective) and objective (real-world) needs. While it emphasizes the learner's role, Hutchinson and Waters (1987) argue for a more collaborative approach involving learners, teachers, and the community.

Strategy analysis: This approach examines the learning styles and strategies employed by language learners (Jordan, 1997). It also distinguishes between "needs," "wants," and "lacks" (Hutchinson & Waters, 1987).

Task-based approach: This approach emphasizes the dynamic qualities of target discourse rather than static text-based analysis. It considers tasks as a key component of needs analysis (Long, 2005).

A learning-centered approach: Hutchinson and Waters (1987) advocate for a learner-centered pedagogical approach, emphasizing the learner's active role in the educational process and advocating for collaborative curriculum development.

Means analysis: This approach focuses on tailoring instruction to specific local contexts and constraints, considering factors such as cultural attitudes, resources, materials, equipment, and methods (Jordan, 1997).

2.4 Related Studies

Studies analysing and investigating learners and their needs are increasingly conducted. At the international level, a wide range of studies can be indicated. Several studies have examined the English

language needs of students in various academic disciplines. Jalil and Kamarudin (2009) explored the needs of Malaysian law students, highlighting the importance of all four language skills for academic and professional success. However, discrepancies emerged between learners and instructors' perceptions of skill priorities. Rajabi and Azarpour (2011) focused on business majors in Iran, emphasizing the crucial role of reading and writing in academic settings, while acknowledging the significance of speaking for professional life. Alastal and Shuib (2012) investigated the English language needs of applied science students, revealing a strong emphasis on reading, listening, and writing skills.

Moving beyond needs analysis, Pichinevskiy (2018) and Bekteshi and Xhaferi (2020) delved into curriculum development and ESP (English for Specific Purposes) in secondary and higher education, respectively. These studies emphasize the importance of tailoring language instruction to specific academic and professional contexts. Finally, Msimeer and Albukbak (2022) highlighted the role of needs analysis in informing language program design, advocating for its continuous implementation.

2.5 Gaps in the Literature

While the reviewed studies contribute significantly to the understanding of language needs in various academic contexts, several gaps emerge in relation to accounting students:

Limited focus on accounting: Most studies have investigated language needs in broader disciplines such as law, business, or science. There is a dearth of research specifically targeting accounting students.

Contextual specificity: While general language needs have been identified, there is a need for in-depth exploration of the specific English language requirements within the accounting field.

Curriculum implications: Although some studies touched on curriculum development, further research is required to examine how identified language needs

- can be effectively translated into specific curriculum components for accounting students..

3. DATA ANALYSIS

The data of this study was collected during the academic year 2023-2024. The data collected was computed and analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). For data reliability, the Alpha test was conducted.

Table 1: Data reliability

Number of questionnaire items	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
65	0.74

A Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.60 indicating good internal consistency and a reliable measure of the underlying construct.

3.1 The Analysis of Students' questionnaires

3.1.1 Accounting students' perceptions toward their English language needs

Axis (A) To what extent the English language skills for studying at the Accounting Department are important?

Table 2: One-Sample T-Test for the importance of English language skills

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-value	Decision
Listening	2.025	.947	-6.512	.000	Important
Speaking	1.900	1.081	-6.434	.000	Important
Reading	1.650	.948	-9.000	.000	Important
Writing	1.800	1.042	-7.279	.000	Important

Table (2) shows that in all statements, the p-value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. Since the mean is less than 3, the opinions of the sample individuals leaned towards the importance of learning basic English language skills within the accounting department.

H₀= There are no important English language needs for accounting students at FEC.

H₁= There are important English language needs for accounting students at FEC.

Table 3: One-Sample T-Test for total score of the axis (A)

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-value	Decision
English Language Skills	1.844	.1586	-14.580	.001	Important

It can be observed that, the opinions of the sample individuals leaned towards the importance of learning basic English language skills within the accounting department.

Axis (B). What are the most important English language sub-skills for studying at the Department of Accounting?

Table 4: *One-Sample T-Test for the importance of English language sub-skills*

H1= There are important English language needs for accounting students at FEC.

Table 3: *One-Sample T-Test for total score of the axis (A)*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-value	Decision
English Language Skills	1.844	.1586	-14.580	.001	Important

It can be observed that, the opinions of the sample individuals leaned towards the importance of learning basic English language skills within the accounting department.

Axis (B). What are the most important English language sub-skills for studying at the Department of Accounting?

Table 4: *One-Sample T-Test for the importance of English language sub-skills*

	The statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Value of T	P-Value	Decision
Reading Sub-Skills	1 Reading Accounting textbooks	2.200	.966	5.237	.000	Important
	2 Reading Accounting articles in journals	2.475	.960	3.457	.001	Important
	3 Reading course handouts	2.425	1.107	3.286	.002	Important
	4 Reading instructions for assignments/projects	2.550	1.011	2.814	.008	Important
Writing Sub-Skills	5 Writing reports	2.425	1.217	2.988	.005	Important
	6 Writing assignments	2.650	1.144	1.934	.060	Moderate
	7 Taking notes in lectures	2.525	1.176	2.554	.015	Important
	8 Answering exams	2.175	1.106	4.714	.000	Important
	9 Writing research papers	2.450	1.011	3.439	.001	Important
	10 Writing summaries	2.625	1.169	2.027	.050	Moderate
Listening Sub-Skills	11 Following and understanding lectures	2.375	1.169	3.379	.002	Important
	12 Listening to oral presentations	2.775	1.073	1.325	.193	Moderate
	13 Following question answer sessions in class	2.375	1.054	3.748	.001	Important
	14 Listening to instructions for assignments	2.800	.939	1.347	.186	Moderate
Speaki	15 Participating in lecture discussions	2.425	1.217	2.988	.005	Important

16	Asking questions in class	2.750	1.235	-1.280	.208	Moderate
17	Giving oral presentations	3.050	1.319	-.240	.812	Moderate
18	Participating in seminars	2.950	1.239	-.255	.800	Moderate
19	Participating in conferences	3.050	1.259	-.251	.803	Moderate

• **The t-test for the total score of the axis (B)**

H0= There are no important sub-skills English language needs for accounting students at FEC.

H1= There are important sub-skills English language needs for accounting students at FEC.

Table 5: *One-Sample T-Test for total score of the axis (B)*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-value	Decision
Sub-Skills	2.582	.258	-7.072	.000	Important

As Table (5) shows the p-value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. Since the mean is less than 3, the opinions of the sample individuals leaned towards the importance of learning the sub-skills of English language within the accounting department.

Axis (C). How proficient are you in the following language skills?

Table 6: *One-Sample T-Test for the proficiency of the English language skills*

English Skills	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-value	Decision
Listening	2.625	1.0546	-2.249	.030	Good
Speaking	3.600	3.011	1.260	.215	Average
Reading	2.525	.960	-3.128	.003	Good

Writing	2.800	.966	- 1.309-	.198	Average
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From Table (6) it can be observed that, the opinions of the sample individuals in the axis (C) the proficiency of English language skills within the accounting department, leaned towards the Average in speaking and writing and to the importance of reading and listening.

• **The t-test for the total score of the axis (C)**

H0= There are no English language lacks for accounting students at FEC.

H1= There are English language lacks for accounting students at FEC.

Table 7: *One-Sample T-Test for total score of the axis (C)*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P- value	Decision
English Language Skills	2.888	.488	- .461-	.676	Average

From Table (7) it can be noticed that, the opinions of the sample members tended towards neutrality in the axis (C) the proficiency in English language skills.

Axis (D). How proficient are you in the following language sub-skills?

Table 8: *One-Sample T-Test for the proficiency of English language sub-skills*

	The statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Value of T	P-Value	Decision
Reading Sub-Skills	1 Reading Accounting textbooks	2.750	1.080	-1.464	.151	Average
	2 Reading Accounting articles in journals	3.000	0.961	.000	1.000	Average
	3 Reading course handouts	2.925	1.071	-.443	.660	Average
	4 Reading instructions for assignments/projects	3.050	0.959	.330	.743	Average
Writing Sub-Skills	5 Writing reports	3.150	1.145	.829	.412	Average
	6 Writing assignments	3.050	1.085	.291	.772	Average
	7 Taking notes in lectures	3.025	1.121	.141	.889	Average
	8 Answering exams	2.800	1.137	-1.113	.273	Average
	9 Writing research papers	3.125	1.244	.635	.529	Average
10 Writing summaries	3.225	1.209	1.177	.246	Average	
Listening Sub-Skills	1 Following and understanding lectures	2.675	1.309	-1.571	.124	Average
	2 Listening to oral presentations	3.000	0.987	.000	1.000	Average
	3 Following question answer sessions in class	2.925	1.269	-.374	.711	Average
	4 Listening to instructions for assignments	3.000	1.155	.000	1.000	Average
Speaking Sub-Skills	5 Participating in lecture discussions	3.100	1.355	.467	.643	Average
	6 Asking questions in class	3.150	1.189	.798	.430	Average
	7 Giving oral presentations	3.450	1.037	2.746	.009	Good
	8 Participating in seminars	3.675	0.944	4.521	.000	Good
	9 Participating in conferences	3.800	0.911	5.551	.000	Good

• **The t-test for the total score of the axis (D)**

H0= There are no English language lacks for accounting students at FEC.

H1= There are English language lacks for accounting students at FEC.

Table 9: One-Sample T-Test for total score of the axis (D)

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-value	Decision
Sub-Skills	3.099	.285	1.511	.148	Average

From Table (9) we noticed that, the opinions of the sample members tended towards neutrality in the axis of the proficiency of English language sub-skills.

Axis (E). How much language training would you like to receive for the following to improve your English language sub-skills?

Table 10: *One-Sample T-Test for language training to improve English language sub-skills*

	The statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Value of T	P-Value	Decision
Reading Sub-Skills	1 Reading Accounting textbooks	2.15	1.099	-4.892-	.000	A lot
	2 Reading Accounting articles in journals	2.65	1.145	-1.934-	.060	Moderate
	3 Reading course handouts	2.5	1.377	-2.296-	.027	A lot
	4 Reading instructions for assignments/projects	2.7	1.305	-1.454-	.154	Moderate
Writing Sub-Skills	5 Writing reports	2.55	1.319	-2.157-	.037	A lot
	6 Writing assignments	2.7	1.381	-1.374-	.177	Moderate
	7 Taking notes in lectures	2.525	1.176	-2.554-	.015	A lot
	8 Answering exams	2.6	1.215	-2.082-	.044	A lot
	9 Writing research papers	2.6	1.411	-1.793-	.081	Moderate
	10 Writing summaries	2.475	1.261	-2.634-	.012	A lot
Listening Sub-Skills	11 Following and understanding lectures	2.475	1.198	-2.772-	.009	A lot
	12 Listening to oral presentations	2.675	1.289	-1.595-	.119	Moderate
	13 Following question answer sessions in class	2.625	1.314	-1.804-	.079	Moderate
	14 Listening to instructions for assignments	2.575	1.318	-2.039-	.048	A lot
Speaking Sub-Skills	15 Participating in lecture discussions	2.7	1.137	-1.669-	.103	Moderate
	16 Asking questions in class	2.625	1.254	-1.891-	.066	Moderate
	17 Giving oral presentations	2.825	1.130	-.980-	.333	Moderate
	18 Participating in seminars	2.925	1.347	-.352-	.727	Moderate
	19 Participating in conferences	2.975	1.405	-.113-	.911	Moderate

The t-test for the total score of the axis (E)

H0= There are no English language wants for accounting students at FEC.

H1= There are English language wants for accounting students at FEC.

Table 11: *One-Sample T-Test for total score of the axis (E)*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-value	Decision
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Sub-Skills	2.624	.179	- 9.153	.000	A lot
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It can be noticed that, the sample members see that they need much of language training to improve their English language sub-skills.

3.2 The Analysis of Lecturers' questionnaires

3.2.1 Accounting lecturers' perceptions toward accounting students' English language needs

Axis (A). To what extent the English language skills for studying at the Accounting Department are important?

Table 12: *One-Sample T-Test for the importance of English language skills*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	P-value	Decision
Listening	1.1538	.37553	-17.725	.000	Important
Speaking	1.5385	.51887	-10.156	.000	Important
Reading	1.2308	.43853	-14.546	.000	Important
Writing	1.5385	.51887	-10.156	.000	Important

Table (12) shows that, the opinions of the sample members tended towards the importance of learning English language skills at the Accounting Department.

- **The t-test for the total score of the axis (A)**

H0= There are no important English language needs for accounting students at FEC.

H1= There are important English language needs for accounting students at FEC.

Table 13: *One-Sample T-Test for total score of the axis (A)*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-value	Decision
English Language Skills	1.36 54	.20234	- 16.1 57	.001	Important

It can be observed that, the opinions of the sample individuals leaned towards the importance of learning basic English language skills within the accounting department.

Axis (B). What are the most important English language sub-

skills for studying at the Department of Accounting?

Table 14: *One-Sample T-Test for the importance of English language sub-skills*

	The statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Value of T	P-Value	Decision
Reading Sub-Skills	1 Reading Accounting textbooks	1.462	.519	-10.690	.000	Important
	2 Reading Accounting articles in journals	1.846	.555	-7.500	.000	Important
	3 Reading course handouts	1.761	.725	-6.121	.000	Important
	4 Reading instructions for assignments/projects	2.077	.494	-6.743	.000	Important
Writing Sub-Skills	5 Writing reports	2.000	.707	-5.099	.000	Important
	6 Writing assignments	2.000	.577	-6.245	.000	Important
	7 Taking notes in lectures	1.539	.519	-10.156	.000	Important
	8 Answering exams	2.000	.408	-8.832	.000	Important
	9 Writing research papers	2.154	.689	-4.430	.001	Important
10 Writing summaries	2.308	.751	-3.323	.006	Important	
Listening Sub-Skills	1 Following and understanding lectures	1.615	.768	-6.501	.000	Important
	2 Listening to oral presentations	2.077	.494	-6.743	.000	Important
	3 Following question answer sessions in class	1.692	.480	-9.815	.000	Important
	4 Listening to instructions for assignments	2.000	.408	-8.832	.000	Important
Speaking Sub-Skills	5 Participating in lecture discussions	1.769	.439	-10.119	.000	Important
	6 Asking questions in class	1.615	.650	-7.675	.000	Important
	7 Giving oral presentations	2.231	.439	-6.325	.000	Important
	8 Participating in seminars	1.923	.862	-4.503	.001	Important
	9 Participating in conferences	1.692	.8549	-5.516	.000	Important

- **The t-test for the total score of the axis (B)**

H₀= There are no important sub-skills English language needs for accounting students at FEC.

H₁= There are important sub-skills English language needs for accounting students at FEC.

Table 15: *One-Sample T-Test for total score of the axis (B)*

	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P-value	Decision
Sub-Skills	1.883	.241	-20.207	.000	Important

As Table (15) shows that, the opinions of the sample individuals leaned towards the importance of learning the sub-skills of English language within the accounting department.

3.3 Comparison Between the Mean responses of lecturers and students

1. Comparison in the axis of English language skills

The Hypothesis:

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$$

$$H_1: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$$

Table 16: *Group Statistics of Means*

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Students	40	7.375	3.614	.571
Lecturers	13	5.461	1.050	.291

The results showed a significant difference between the Mean evaluation of lecturers and students of the main English language skills, as the Mean evaluation of lecturers was 5.46, while the Mean evaluation of students was 7.37. This indicates a difference in the two parties' view of the importance of these skills.

Table 17: *Independent Samples Test*

	t	P-value
Equal variances assumed	1.872	.015
Equal variances not assumed	2.983	.004

From Table (17) we notice that p-value = 0.015 less than 0.05 this means that the variance is not equal in the two samples. Since the variance is not equal we take p-value = 0.004 less than 0.05 this means that the averages of the professors' and students' answers are not equal.

2. Comparison in the axis of English language sub-skills

The Hypothesis:

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$$

$$H_1: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$$

Table 18: *Group Statistics of Means*

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
students	40	49.050	14.498	2.292
lecturers	13	35.769	4.549	1.262

From Table (18) we notice that the Mean of the lecturers' answers in the sub-skills is 35.76 and the Mean of the students' answers is 49.05.

Table 19: *Independent Samples Test*

	t	P-value
Equal variances assumed	3.233	.006
Equal variances not assumed	5.076	.000

From Table (19) it shows that p-value = 0.006 less than 0.05. This means that the variance is not equal in the two samples. Since the variance is not equal then p-value = 0.000 less than 0.05 can be taken. This means that the averages of the lecturers' and students' answers are not equal.

From the two comparisons demonstrates that the Mean of the lecturers' answers and the Mean of the students' answers are different and there is a difference between them due to the difference in educational level, age and job opportunities offered to the individuals of the two samples.

4. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Findings

The study findings indicate that both accounting students and lecturers perceive all English language skills as essential. Furthermore, they also consider all language sub-skills to be important.

As for the language lacks, Based on their own assessment, accounting students believe they possess a high level of listening and reading skills, but consider their

speaking and writing skills to be average. As for the sub-skills, the students have assigned all the sub-skill that they lack all or that they are weak proficient in all sub-skill.

The accounting students expressed a substantial requirement for language training to enhance English language sub-skill competencies. The study has shown that students hope to get

training in all the suggested sub-skills.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study on the English language needs of accounting students, the following recommendations are presented to enhance English language proficiency and academic performance in the field of Accounting:

1. Based on the findings, it is evident that accounting students require proficiency in all four language skills to excel in their academic pursuits. To address their specific needs, any English for Specific Purposes (ESP) course designed for accounting students should prioritize speaking and writing, as these skills are deemed most crucial by both students and lecturers.
2. The findings of this study are significant for lecturers and course designers, as they provide valuable guidance for selecting, classifying, sequencing, or ordering materials in ESP course design.
3. Prior to course development, students' English proficiency levels must be accurately assessed. Furthermore, learners should be guided in understanding their current language abilities and the English language proficiency required for their field of study.
4. Students should complete additional English language courses prior to beginning their study of accounting to ensure they are adequately prepared for any expected ESP courses.
5. The currently offered course should be consolidated and supported by other courses that take into account different language aspects such as technical vocabulary- accounting terminology.
6. Cooperation between the Accounting Department and the English Department is recommended. Various events (workshops, training sessions, meetings with English speaking people, etc.) can be organized in order to help students and lecturers practice and use the language effectively in their discipline and promote their language proficiency.

4.3 Conclusion

It is anticipated that this study, to some extent, has identified the English language requirements of accounting students at the Faculty of Economics and Commerce (FEC). This foundation can serve as a robust

framework for course designers to develop targeted English for Accounting Purposes courses aligned with the needs of accounting majors. English language proficiency, particularly in reading and writing, is a critical gap in the preparation of the accounting students targeted in this study. Despite recognizing the importance of all language skills, students exhibit specific weaknesses in speaking and writing. By implementing the early mentioned recommendations, the study anticipates improved English language skills among accounting students, leading to enhanced academic performance and better preparation for professional life.

References

- Alastal, A., & Shuib, M. (2012). Investigating the Academic English Language Target Needs of Undergraduates at The Faculty of Applied Science at Al-Aqsa University: Students' perceptions. *The Asian ESP Journal*, 8(2), 5-26.
- Al-Tamimi, A., & Shuib, M. (2010). Investigating the English Language Needs of Petroleum Engineering Students at Hadhramout University of Science and Technology. *The Asian ESP Journal*, 6(1), 6-34. Retrieved July 10, 2024, from <https://www.asian-esp-journal.com/april-2010/>
- Anonymous. (2024). Retrieved in July7, 2024, from https://asmarya.edu.ly/economy/?page_id=1361
- Bekteshi, E., & Xhaferi, B. (2020). An Analysis of English for Specific Purposes Among University Students. *Educational Process: International Journal*, 9(2), 90-102.
- Ben-Madani, M. (2016). Theses Abstracts in English on Libya 1936–2012. *The Maghreb Review* 41(1), 3-255. <https://doi.org/10.1353/tmr.2016.0009>.
- Dudley-Evans, T., & John, M. (1998). *Developments in ESP: A Multi-Disciplinary Approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Goh, C. C. M. (2013). ESP and Listening. In B. Paltridge, & S. Starfield. (Eds.), *The Handbook of English for Specific Purposes*, 55-76. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Harmer, J. (2001). *The Practice of English Language Teaching (3rd ed.)*. London: Longman.
- Hirvela, A. (2013). ESP and Reading. In B. Paltridge, & S. Starfield. (Eds.), *The Handbook of English for Specific Purposes*, (77-94). Malden, MA: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Hutchinson, T., & Waters, A. (1987). *English for Specific Purposes: A Learning-Centered Approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Hyland, K. (2013). ESP and Writing. In B. Paltridge, & S. Starfield. (Eds.), *The Handbook of English for Specific Purposes*, (95-113). Malden, MA: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Jalil, N., & Kamarudin, M. (2009). ELAP Needs Analysis for Law Students. *Journal of Human Capital Development*, 2(2), 121-136.
- Jordan, R. (1997). *English for Academic Purposes: A Guide and Resource Book for Teachers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Long, M. H. (2005). Methodological Issues in Learner Needs Analysis. In M. H. Long (Ed.), *Second Language Needs Analysis*, (19-76). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- McDonough, J. (1984). *ESP in Perspective: A Practical Guide*. Collins ELT.
- Mosbah, A.Y. S. (2018). *The Required Knowledge and Skills From Libyan University Accounting Education and Barriers to Development: A Mixed Methods Study Using an Institutional Theory Lens*. [Doctoral Thesis, University of Huddersfield]. <https://eprints.hud.ac.uk/id/eprint/34773/>
- Mohsen, A. S. (2014). Teaching English as a Foreign Language in Libya. *Scientific Research Journal*, 2(11), 58-64. <https://www.scirj.org/papers-1114/scirj-P1114206.pdf>
- Msimeer, A & Albukbak, O. (2022). Libyan Teachers' Perceptions of Needs Analysis Use in English Language Programmes. *The Academic Research Journal: Humanities Science*, 22, 13-24. <https://lam.edu.ly/ar/images/acadj/issue22/02Ensanya.pdf>
- Pichinevskiy, S. (2018). *Developing an ESP Curriculum on Tourism and Agribusiness for a Rural School in Nicaragua: a Retrospective Diary*, [Masters Thesis, EWU Masters Thesis Collection. 521]. <https://dc.ewu.edu/theses/521>
- Rajabi, P., & Azarpour, N. (2011). Academic Needs of Iranian Business Administration Students in ESP Classes. *Contemporary Online Language Education Journal*, 1, 20-32. <https://www.ajindex.com/dosyalar/makale/acarindex-1423874780.pdf>
- Ramadan, M.O. (2020). Libyan Students' High Marks and Low Academic Performance: Case Study in the English Department at Sirte University. In: Omar, Y. Z. (Ed) *Teaching and Learning English as a Foreign Language in Libyan Higher Education Setting*. (241-261) Democratic Arab Center Strategic, Political & Economic studies, Berlin.
- Richards, J. C. (2001). *Curriculum Development in Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.